

POTENTIAL OF STRONGLY COUPLED TIME DOMAIN FSI SIMULATIONS ON THE EXAMPLE OF THE ARIAS CTA LPT ROTOR

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ABSTRACT

In this work a recently developed Fluid-Structure Interaction (FSI) solver is applied on the low-pressure turbine bladed rotor from the second Work Package of the ARIAS EU project, where, among other things, occurrence of amplitude-limited flutter under different operating conditions was investigated. Results of the involved single field models and their combination in well known linear methods are compared to the respective measurements from the cold-flow experimental campaign at CTA and the spin-pit test campaign at Avios STARGATE-Rig. In the course of this paper, a study is also presented that compares different time step sizes using both explicit and implicit coupling schemes within our time-domain FSI solver. The influence of this time step size on the instabilities from the added mass effect on the one hand and the potential to stabilize the FSI simulations with the implicit coupling scheme on the other hand are investigated. It is shown, that the accuracy and stability of the FSI solver are highly sensitive to both the selected time discretization and the coupling strategy, including their mutual interplay.

Keywords: Aeroelasticity, Time-Domain FSI, Implicit Coupling

1 INTRODUCTION

Increasing demands on the efficiency of aviation engines require new materials and thinner, and thus lighter, designs of turbomachinery blades. As a result, the aeroelastic evaluation of components is becoming increasingly important to ensure safety. Therefore the methods needed for design are continuously evolving especially in the field of multidisciplinary design. An

attractive and potentially the most accurate approach right now are fully coupled fluid-structure interaction (FSI) simulations in the time domain [1]. Following a partitioned coupling approach, one of the biggest challenges is to exchange the boundary conditions between the involved solvers at the right point in time and as accurate as possible to ensure correct simulation of the physical phenomena. If implicit (strong) coupling is used here, i.e. the multiple iteration of a physical coupling time step, the convergence of the transferred boundary conditions can be ensured. In contrast, the use of explicit (weak) coupling may lead to a loss of accuracy and can introduce stability challenges related to the added-mass effect [2]. In this paper we investigate the impact of the chosen time step size on the coupled simulation, especially in the context of benefits of the implicit coupling scheme against an explicit one. The model for this study is evaluated on the basis of a comparison with test data of the CTA turbine from the ARIAS project [3]. As a prerequisite, we built the aerodynamic and structure mechanic models and validated single field computations against the measurements from the respective ARIAS test campaigns. Subsequently, established aeroelastic simulation methods were applied to assess the quality of the aeroelastic predictions based on the employed models. Finally, the focus is placed on a study examining the impact of time discretization and coupling strategy on the performance and accuracy of the developed fully coupled time-domain FSI solver.

We begin by presenting the developed FSI solver and providing the methodological background on the added-mass effect and implicit coupling, followed by a description of the test case and its experimental investigation. In Section 4, we then present the main results of our simulations conducted within the scope of this work.

2 METHODOLOGY

This section provides a concise overview of the primary method investigated in this work, a fully coupled FSI Solver. Other standard methods used to obtain presented results are well established and therefore not discussed in detail here.

2.1 FSI solver

The recently developed fully coupled time-domain FSI solver [4] integrates the finite-volume flow solver TRACE (Turbomachinery Research Aerodynamic Computational Environment) with the finite element method (FEM) solver CalculiX via surface coupling, facilitated by the coupling library preCICE. In this setup, fluid forces computed by TRACE are transferred to CalculiX and applied as surface loads. Conversely, the structural displacements and velocities computed by CalculiX are passed back to TRACE, where they serve as boundary conditions for the integrated mesh deformation solver. This coupling is illustrated in Figure 1. To enable communication between the solvers the library's application programming interface (API) is integrated into each solver through minimally invasive adapters embedded in their respective routines.

FIGURE 1. CONNECTION BETWEEN PRECICE AND BOTH SOLVERS.

On the fluid side, the solver employs TRACE, a CFD code developed by the DLR Institute of Propulsion Technology and MTU Aero Engines AG [5]. TRACE is specifically designed for simulating complex turbomachinery flows and is widely used in industrial environments for the design and optimization of turbomachinery components. For structural analysis, the solver utilizes the open-source FEM software CalculiX [6], which is also developed at MTU Aero Engines AG and thus possesses a strong foundation in turbomachinery applications. The coupling between TRACE and CalculiX is managed by preCICE, an open-source library for partitioned multi-physics simulations. preCICE is primarily developed by the Chair of Scientific Computing at the Technical University of Munich and the Institute for Parallel and Distributed Systems at the University of Stuttgart [7].

2.1.1 Fluid – TRACE In TRACE, the unsteady Reynolds-averaged Navier–Stokes (URANS) equations are discretized using the finite-volume method. Turbulence is modeled via the $k-\omega$ model proposed by Wilcox [8] and transition is covered by the multi mode model proposed by Kozulovic [9]. Furthermore we make use of the Kato-Launder Stagnation Point Fix [10]. To account for the deformation of the solid domain, a moving fluid mesh is employed. The governing equations are formulated in an Arbitrary Lagrangian–Eulerian (ALE) framework and spatially discretized on a structured grid using a second-order Fromm scheme with a Van Albada limiter [11]. Temporal discretization is performed using a second-order Euler-backward scheme combined with a predictor–corrector method. At the inflow and outflow boundaries, two-dimensional frequency-domain boundary conditions are applied [12, 13]. Mesh deformation is handled by solving a Laplace equation using a GMRES solver, which is initialized at each time step with the deformation from the previous step. As part of this work, the preCICE adapter for TRACE was extended to support implicit coupling.

2.1.2 Solid – CalculiX On the structural side, the equations of motion are solved using the finite element method implemented in CalculiX. The *Dynamic Analysis Mode* [6], which computes the structural response to dynamic loading via direct integration of the discretized equations of motion is used. The preCICE adapter for CalculiX was extended to work with its latest version.

2.1.3 Interface – preCICE The interface between the fluid and solid domains is where the governing equations of both fields interact through their boundary conditions. Structural deformation influences the fluid mesh domain, while aerodynamic forces acting on the blade serve as external loads in the structural equations. To capture these interactions, TRACE and CalculiX must exchange boundary data effectively. Beyond data exchange, preCICE provides advanced interpolation techniques that eliminate the need for matching mesh discretizations at the interface. Additionally, preCICE manages time-stepping, ensuring consistent data exchange across solvers even when they operate with different time increments. The configuration of preCICE allows control over the coupling scheme, including parallel or serial execution of solvers and explicit or implicit coupling strategies. Different acceleration methods for implicit coupling are supported, e.g. under-relaxation. Communication between the solvers takes place at a lean peer-to-peer level so that only the processes of each solver that 'share' an associated surface part communicate with each other via MPI.

2.2 Implicit coupling and added-mass effect

A key challenge in aeroelastic simulations of turbomachinery components is the accurate and stable representation of FSI under compressible flow conditions. One of the primary destabilizing factors is the added-mass effect, which arises when a moving structure accelerates surrounding fluid, effectively increasing the system's inertia. In partitioned FSI approaches — where fluid and structural solvers operate independently and exchange data at discrete time intervals — this effect can lead to numerical instabilities. To avoid these instabilities, there are two possible approaches. One can either choose a very small coupling time step in an explicitly coupled scheme, or employ implicit coupling. In the former, data is exchanged only once per coupling time window while the latter enables iterative convergence of the exchanged quantities (e.g., displacements, forces) within each coupling time interval. As a result, error propagation can be minimized, and — depending on the strength of the added-mass effect — significantly more accurate simulation results can be achieved. The choice of time step size also plays a crucial role, as the added-mass effect in compressible fluids is localized and propagates at the speed of sound, allowing for stabilization through appropriate selection of the coupling time interval. The fixed-point equation for the FSI coupling algorithm can be written as

$$\mathbf{x}^{(k+1)} = \mathcal{S} \circ \mathcal{F}(\mathbf{x}^{(k)}),$$

where $\mathbf{x}^{(k)}$ represents the interface variables (e.g., displacements or forces) at iteration k , \mathcal{F} denotes the fluid solver, and \mathcal{S} the structural solver.

This composition can be expressed as a single coupling operator,

$$\mathcal{H} = \mathcal{S} \circ \mathcal{F},$$

so that the fixed-point iteration becomes

$$\mathbf{x}^{(k+1)} = \mathcal{H}(\mathbf{x}^{(k)}).$$

According to the Banach fixed-point theorem, convergence is thus guaranteed in every coupling time interval if and only if the operator is a contraction with operator norm less than one, i.e.,

$$\|\mathcal{H}\| < 1.$$

The contraction of a function is defined as

$$\|\mathbf{x}^{(k+1)} - \mathbf{x}^{(k)}\|_2 \leq k \|\mathbf{x}_1 - \mathbf{x}_0\|_2$$

with contraction constant k

$$k \in [0, 1).$$

According to Van Brummelen [2], the upper bound for the contraction constant k in the fixed-point equation of the implicitly coupled FSI simulation is given by the ratio of the added mass μ_k to the structural mass m_s . The necessary condition for contraction is therefore:

$$k \leq \frac{\mu_k}{m_s} < 1$$

For compressible fluids, pressure fluctuations originating from the displacement of the interaction interface propagate at the speed of sound c , and thus have only a local effect on the fluid field over the propagation distance ct . The magnitude of the added mass for compressible fluids is given by

$$\mu_k = \rho_f c t$$

Thus, there exists a strictly positive time step size Δt for all combinations of structural mass m_s and fluid density ρ_f , for which the fixed-point iteration of the implicit FSI coupling is numerically stable.

If the time step becomes too small or to accelerate the convergence, the fixed-point iteration of the implicit coupling can be extended by a stabilization technique in the form of under-relaxation to ensure contraction of the solution per coupling time step. For the partitioned approach with preCICE, a constant under-relaxation, Aitken under-relaxation, or quasi-Newton methods can be used [7]. The modified fixed-point iteration using a constant under-relaxation, that is utilized within this work, reads:

$$\mathbf{x}^{(k+1)} = \mathbf{x}^{(k)} + \omega \left(\mathcal{H}(\mathbf{x}^{(k)}) - \mathbf{x}^{(k)} \right)$$

where $\omega \in (0, 1)$ is the relaxation parameter. To conclude, the convergence and thus success of the simulation depends highly on the choice of the coupling scheme and time discretization, which we investigate in the studies presented in this work.

3 TEST CASE AND MODELING

The following section describes the test case under investigation, highlighting its defining aeroelastic characteristics and operational conditions. Furthermore the measurement results are depicted and the modeling for our FSI scenario is outlined.

3.1 ARIAS CTA Turbine test case

Within the framework of the ARIAS EU project, an isolated turbine bladed disk was investigated in the CTA Cold Flow Rig. The experimental setup, see Figure 2, is a continuation of that used in the FUTURE project and is very similar. The primary objective of the investigation was, among other aspects, the study of flutter phenomena using high-quality blade tip timing (BTT) signals. The blade turning, the investigated Mach number, and the Reynolds number correspond to those of a subsonic low-pressure turbine. The nominal operating point is characterized by $M_{in} = 0.42$, $M_{out} = 0.75$, $Re = 1.2 \times 10^5$ and flow angles $\alpha_{in} = 36,5^\circ$, $\alpha_{out} = 60^\circ$. The turbine blade, with an aspect ratio of approximately 5.3, is manufactured from aluminum. The reduced frequency for the first Eigenmode at the nominal operating point is approximately 0.1. The disk is made of steel and is therefore relatively stiff compared to the blade, resulting in flat frequency nodal diameter (ND) curves, see Figure 3. In total, 144 cantilevered blades are mounted in the fir-tree disk slots.

FIGURE 2. CTA TEST RIG SETUP AND INSTRUMENTATION (FROM [3])

As depicted in Figure 2 the test rig is instrumented with five-hole probes mounted on traversing rakes, which can map 28° sectors at both the inlet and outlet measurement planes. Furthermore, blade vibration amplitudes were measured using Blade-TipTiming (BTT) probes, and unsteady pressure sensors enabled additional investigations. All measurements were conducted in a non-intrusive or minimally intrusive manner to minimize disturbance of the flow.

During the test campaign, various operating points were investigated. Parameters such as rotational speed, density, exit Mach number were varied and different mistuning patterns and under-platform dampers were studied. Furthermore the magnetic excitation of specific engine orders was supported.

FIGURE 3. NODAL DIAMETER CURVES FOR THE FIRST TWO EIGENMODES

3.2 Experimental results

As the results of the low-pressure turbine bladed rotor from the second Work Package of the ARIAS EU project, investigated at CTA were discussed and published in several other works, e.g. [3], [14], [15] and [16], we turn our attention to a concise summary of the key findings that are most relevant for our work. Due to the chosen design, the blade is prone to flutter, which was observed at the majority of operating points. The signals obtained from the unsteady pressure sensors correlate well with the vibrations measured by the BTT probes. Interaction between flutter and forced response, mistuning patterns and dampers were investigated, nevertheless we focus on flutter behavior of the base configuration. Mode 1 flutter occurs for all speed levels and an approximate proportional dependence of the saturation amplitude on the facility's mass flow is observed. As outlined in [14] and [3], the non-synchronous signals measured with the BTT probes and the unsteady pressure transducers indicate, that especially the Nodal Diameters around -30 tend to be the most unstable. In Figure 4 the BTT signal for the off-design condition at 62% speed is shown. Non-synchronous flutter contributions from the second mode were indicated under those off-design conditions, aligning well with the subsequent numerical findings, see Section 4.2.

FIGURE 4. BTT SIGNAL OF THE CTA COLD FLOW TESTS AT REDUCED SPEED OF $N=62\%$ (FROM [3])

3.3 Modeling

The unsteady time-domain RANS simulations were performed using a structured fluid mesh comprising around 480.000 cells. Non-reflecting two-dimensional frequency boundary conditions were applied at both the inflow and outflow boundaries. The flow conditions are defined by the experiment as described in Section 3.1 and set as follows. At the inlet, the measured total pressure, total temperature and inflow angles are prescribed, as well as Turbulence Intensity and Length Scale. The measured back pressure is given at the outlet. The structural model of the blade consists of 3.250 eight-node hexahedral (brick) elements. The material properties were chosen according to Section 3.1. For now, stick contact conditions were applied at the interface between the blade and the disk. Structural simulations were conducted using CalculiX, employing dynamic analysis. For coupling via preCICE, a serial coupling scheme was adopted with nearest-neighbor mapping. Pressure data were transferred from TRACE to CalculiX, while displacements and velocities were communicated in the reverse direction. The base simulation relies on a single passage model was executed with 128 time steps per period at a frequency in TRACE that corresponds to the first bending mode of the blade, resulting in a time step size of approximately $4 \times 10^{-5}s$. In all calculations the coupling time interval equals the time step size of both solvers. The steady-state flow solution, which serves as the initial condition for the unsteady simulation, is presented in Figure 5. To compare the conducted studies for the FSI simulations, the blade deflection is analyzed at the trailing edge region close to the blade tip, referred to as analysis point in the following.

FIGURE 5. FLOW PATH AROUND THE BLADE AT 50% RELATIVE CHANNEL HEIGHT

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this section the main results of our simulations are shown, starting with single field validations of our models, followed by

conventional aeroelastic simulations, and ultimately with focus on our parameter study for fully coupled fluid–structure interaction (FSI) simulations.

4.1 Aero and structure single field validation

Initially, a stationary aerodynamic calculation with the TRACE flow solver is considered using a single passage model of the rotor flow field from the CTA Test Facility’s wind tunnel. Given the inlet boundary conditions and the back pressure for the nominal point at Mach=0.675, N=103%, rho=100%, the mass-flow, outflow angle, total pressure and temperature profile at the outlet are compared with the corresponding measurement data. Figure 6 shows the simulated and measured total pressure distribution at the outlet plane. For both, numerical and experimental data, the radial distributions have been generated by means of a circumferential mass average. Unfortunately, at present, no uncertainty estimates are available to us for the experimental data. Good agreement between our simulations and the experimental measurements could be observed for several operating conditions.

FIGURE 6. COMPARISON OF THE MEASURED AND SIMULATED TOTAL PRESSURE DISTRIBUTION AT THE OUTLET PLANE

Furthermore, a frequency analysis of a CalculiX model of one blade and the corresponding disk segment is performed and the results are compared to the measured frequencies from the spin-rig test of the ARIAS project. Figure 7 shows the first two Eigenmodes of the structural simulation. Their frequency curves were already shown in Figure 3.

In conclusion, the single-field models are deemed appropriate, and we now proceed with the aeroelastic investigation of the test case.

FIGURE 7. APPEARANCE OF THE FIRST TWO EIGENMODES OF THE BLADE

4.2 Flutter computation for nominal operating and off-design conditions

To validate the aeroelastic behavior of the models, we conducted an aeroelastic simulation that accounts for the structural deformation based on the previously computed mode shapes. Consequently, the mesh deformation is represented as a linear combination of these modes. The aerodynamics are solved with the Harmonic Balance (HB) Method in TRACE [17]. Within the HB calculations we considered the first four Harmonics and took the same settings for turbulence and transition as in all other calculations, described in Section 2.1.1. The resulting flutter-curves for the first two modes are shown in Figure 8 and Figure 9 for the nominal operating point at 103% speed and an off-design-point at 62% speed.

The numerical results for the first mode demonstrate significant instability at around Nodal Diameter -30 for both operating points. This coincides well with the results from the measurements outlined in Section 3.2. For the second mode, a trend towards increasing instability at the off-design operating point is qualitatively detectable, as the damping value decreases towards zero for Nodal Diameters around 35. The simulation at this stage employs a simplified discretization and numerical approach. Therefore we consider the described trend towards instability as good alignment with the instabilities for the second mode in off-design conditions indicated by the measurements as outlined in Section 3.2, even if the computed damping value does not fall below zero. To conclude, we assess the aeroelastic properties of the models to be sufficiently accurate to serve as a reliable basis for our fluid-structure interaction (FSI) simulations.

FIGURE 8. FLUTTER CURVES FOR EIGENMODE 1

FIGURE 9. FLUTTER CURVES FOR EIGENMODE 2

4.3 Study on coupling scheme and time step size for FSI simulations

Currently, the fully coupled fluid-structure interaction (FSI) simulations are based on a single-passage model and without Phase-Lag Boundary Conditions. As a result, the actual vibration modes cannot be resolved as only the mode with nodal diameter zero can be realized. Furthermore, with stick contact condition between disk and blade in the structure model we would not expect the vibration amplitude to be saturated. Thus, the analysis is limited to a comparative assessment of the method's parameters. For future work, the FSI simulations are planned to be extended to a full-annulus model also incorporating a nonlinear contact formulation, thereby allowing for a direct validation against experimental observations. For now we studied the sensitivity of the vibration simulations to the time step size in conjunction with the coupling scheme.

The results for varying time steps per period in the case of explicit coupling are presented in Figure 10 and Figure 11. In Figure 10 the displacement of our analysis point (described in Section 3.3) is plotted over time for up to around 370 periods.

Compared to each other, the simulations show overall agreement in their results. Nevertheless, cases with coarser time discretization (green and red curves) display a tendency toward more significant overshoots. For discretizations of 128 time steps per period (blue) and above (black, orange), the resulting signals exhibit strong consistency and are qualitatively comparable, as can be especially seen in the zoom in of the signal in Figure 11.

FIGURE 10. DISPLACEMENT OF THE BLADE'S ANALYSIS POINT OVER TIME FOR DIFFERENT TIME STEPS PER PERIOD (TSPP), EXPLICIT COUPLING

FIGURE 11. ZOOM IN ON DISPLACEMENT OF THE BLADE'S ANALYSIS POINT OVER TIME FOR DIFFERENT TIME STEPS PER PERIOD (TSPP), EXPLICIT COUPLING

A comparison between implicit and explicit coupling was carried out for several temporal discretizations. In the following, 128 time steps per period are considered. Figure 12 shows the displacement of our analysis point over time for around 150 pe-

riods. Figure 13 again provides a detailed zoom into a time window covering eight oscillation cycles. Considering both plots, the following becomes evident: while the asymptotic value of the damped oscillation agrees well between both simulations, the transient vibration behavior differs significantly. The simulation using implicit coupling shows a markedly reduced oscillation amplitude and, as indicated by the logarithmic decrement of the curve of the peaks in Figure 12, demonstrates stronger damping characteristics than the explicit coupling approach. Thus we conclude, that the choice of the coupling scheme is very important to quantitatively reproduce amplitudes from the experimental findings in future work.

FIGURE 12. DISPLACEMENT OF THE BLADE'S ANALYSIS POINT OVER TIME, EXPLICIT VS: IMPLICIT COUPLING

FIGURE 13. ZOOM IN ON DISPLACEMENT OF THE BLADE'S ANALYSIS POINT OVER TIME, EXPLICIT VS: IMPLICIT COUPLING

FIGURE 14. DISPLACEMENT OF THE BLADE’S ANALYSIS POINT OVER TIME FOR DIFFERENT TIME STEPS PER PERIOD (TSPP), IMPLICIT COUPLING

Now we compared different time discretizations in simulations with an implicit coupling scheme. Figure 14 shows a comparison between simulations with 128 time steps per period (orange) on the one hand and 64 time steps per period (blue) on the other hand. Both simulations are very similar and the asymptotic value of the damped oscillation agrees well again. Nevertheless, the coarser time step shows a slightly different damping of the oscillation resulting in a lower amplitude over time. This differs from the results with the explicit coupling scheme, where coarser time steps tend to be more prone to overshoots.

All in all we observe high sensitivity of the simulations regarding time discretization and choice of the coupling scheme.

5 CONCLUSIONS AND OUTLOOK

The developed FSI solver was applied to the ARIAS CTA turbine test case and evaluated in terms of its sensitivity to the choice of temporal discretization and coupling scheme. The simulated vibrational response of the investigated blade was found to be highly sensitive to the interplay between those two parameters. Implicit coupling demonstrates its potential primarily by enabling the use of larger time steps despite instabilities induced by the added-mass effect, without compromising the accuracy of the results. Further investigations are required to better understand influences on the accuracy of the developed FSI solver. Future work will focus on extending the models to full-annulus configurations and incorporating nonlinear contact formulations between the disk and the blade. These enhancements are expected to enable the simulations to quantitatively or at least qualitatively reproduce the saturation amplitudes observed in the experiments. Moreover, the choice of temporal discretization and coupling scheme will remain a critical factor in achieving reliable and accurate results.

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